

Spatial Analysis of Water Quality in Loikaw Town, Kayah State

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Abstract

Loikaw Township is located in the Kayah State, the urban growth is gradually increased in the city and rural areas are quite different with socio-economic conditions and its infrastructure development in the study area. Domestic water use of the study area is one of the basic factor to estimate volume of water consumption of an area because of domestic water use is related the systematically water supply system. This study only concerns with the loikaw urban area covering Loikaw Township which has water deterioration and water scarcity area in the summer. In this paper, geospatial data from the field survey, water quality data from the experimental lab, and secondary derived from administrative Office. Method of this study, Water Quality compare with WHO Standard, weight overlay analysis as the combined use of spatial (Geostatistics). Finally result of the water quality suitability area zone of Loikaw Town.

Key Words: Water Quality, Geospatial, Geostatistics

Introduction

Water is important for natural ecosystems and human development. It is important for various activities such as drinking, cooking, industry, agriculture and recreation. In the human body, it is also used to transport, dissolve organic matter and add nutrients while carrying waste materials. Water is a vital component of the biosphere containing less than one percent of the world's freshwater with its higher ecological and social significance which are being polluted by indiscriminate disposal of sewerage waste, indiscriminate industrial waste, and by human activities that affect their physical and chemical characteristics and lead to various damaging effects on aquatic organisms. Water quality provides up-to-date information about the concentration of various solutes in a particular place and time. The quality parameters provide a basis for assessing the suitability of water for designated use and to improve existing conditions. The deterioration of water quality has led to the destruction of ecosystem balance, contamination and contamination of soil and surface water sources. Water quality can be regarded as a variable network such as pH, oxygen concentration, temperature, etc. and any changes in these physical and chemical variables can affect aquatic biota in various ways. Since water quality is directly related to health and important for the determination of water utilities, it is very important and important to test water quality before being used for drinking, domestic, agricultural or industrial purposes. This study only concerns with the Loikaw urban area covering Loikaw Township which has water deterioration and water scarcity area in the summer. In this paper, geospatial data from the field survey, water quality data from the experimental lab, and secondary derived from administrative Office. This study Water Quality compare with WHO Standard, weight overlay analysis as the combined use of spatial (Geostatistics). Finally result of the water quality suitability area zone of Loikaw Town.

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Study Area

Study area is located between the 19°38' 43.945" and 19°42' 29.084" North latitude and between 97°11' 16.885" and 97°14' 18.165" East longitude. It is located in the Loikaw Township, Kayah State in Myanmar. It comprises 19 wards of the Loikaw town. The 125 sampling points of the study area are randomly selected using GPS (global positioning systems) of 19 wards in Loikaw town.

Figure. 1 Location of the Study Area in Loikaw town, Loikaw Township, Kayah State, Myanmar

Sources : Topographic Map (1:50000 and Google Earth image SPORT 5, 2.5 meter resolution)

Sources of Data and Methodology

Based map and road data are derived from the topographic map (1:50000) and google earth map (2017). Other secondary data derived from the Township Administrative Office of Loikaw Township. Water quality data from the field survey, 2018 March and the 125 sampling points of the study area are randomly selected using GPS (global positioning systems) and

water quality tester of 19 ward in Loikaw town. Other chemical parameters are tested from the laboratory. In this paper, the method of water quality parameter compared with WHO standard and distribution of water quality are used for geospatial analysis and geostatistical analysis.

Spatial Variation of Water quality in Loikaw Town

The physical, chemical and bacterial characteristics of groundwater determine its usefulness for various purposes. In this study, the physiochemical test is mainly used to analyze the contents of Temperature, pH (Hydrogen ions), Electric Conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Salinity, Iron (Fe), Magnesium (Mg), Cadmium (Cd), Copper (Cu) and Lead (Pb). The groundwater quality values are compared with assessment WHO standard.

1. Temperature

As temperature has an influence on many other aquatic variables and processes, it is important always to include in a sample region, and record it at the time of collecting water samples. The solubility of oxygen in water decreases as a water temperature increases. Temperature should be measured by thermometer. In Loikaw, the lowest value of water temperature is 25.8°C in Lawdama ward and the highest value of water temperature is 28.7°C in Nyaungya B, Figure 2.1 (a) and (b).

Figure. 2 (a) and (b) Water Temperature of the study area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

2. pH

pH values vary from a minimum of 7.47 ± 0.208 and a maximum of 8.40 ± 0.964 . These values are within the permissible limit of WHO and FAO set for drinking and irrigation purposes. The optimum pH requirement usually in different water supplies according to the composition of the water and the nature of the construction material used in the distribution system, but it is usually in the range of 6.5-8 mg/l (WHO, 2011). In the study area, the lowest pH value in the Loikaw Town is observed in Htaythama ward as 5.6. The highest pH value is

7.39 of Nyaungya A ward area in Figure 3 (a) and (b). It is neutral at pH 7, acidic if it is less than 7 and alkaline if it is more than 7. If the pH value is outside the range of desired level or permissible level) it should be considered whether or not to human use as drinking water.

Figure. 3 (a) and (b) pH of the study area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

3. Electrical Conductivity (EC)

The electrical conductivity of water estimates the total amount of solids dissolved in water. The electrical conductivity is a measure to the capacity of water to conduct electrical current; it is directly related to the concentration of salts dissolved in water. Electrical conductivity is actually a measure of the ionic activity of a solution in term of its capacity to transmit current. As the solution becomes more concentrated ($EC > 2000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), the proximity of the solution ions to each other depresses their activity and consequently their ability to transmit current, although the physical amount of dissolved solids is not affected. The measurement of product conductivity is a typical way to monitor and continuously trend the performance of water purification systems. The minimum value of electrical conductivity occurs at Htaythama ward area $283 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The maximum value of electrical conductivity is $1149 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ at Nampawwam A ward area shown in Figure 2(a) and a(b).

Figure. 4 (a) and (b) Electrical Conductivity (EC) of Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

4. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

According to WHO (1984), the palatability of water with a Total Dissolved Solids level with rating of less than 500 mg/l is generally considered to be excellent, drinking water becomes significantly. High concentrations of dissolved solids of about 3000 mg/l may also produce distress in livestock (PunamTyagi, 2003). Primary sources for higher TDS in the river water might be due to agricultural runoff, discharge of domestic waste from the town and other human activities like washing of different vehicle. Total Dissolved Solids comprise inorganic salts and small amounts of organic matter that are dissolved in the water. Total Dissolved Solids in drinking water originates from natural sources, sewage, urban runoff and industrial wastewater. According to the test result of 125 samples, Total Dissolved Solids range between 202 ppm in Htaythama ward and 818 ppm in Dawohgu ward. Groundwater on the basis of WHO standard the higher desire level of Total Dissolved Solids is 500 ppm and maximum permissible level is 1500 ppm figure 5 (a) and (b).

Figure. 5 (a) and (b) Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) of Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

5. Salinity

Salts and other substances affect the quality of water used for irrigation or drinking. They also have a critical influence on aquatic biota, and every kind of organism has a typical salinity range that it can tolerate. Salinity is a measure of how much dissolved salts are in the water. Salinity is produced by natural processes such as weathering of rocks and wind and rain depositing salt over thousands of years. Human activities also affect salinity levels in ground and surface water. Application of synthetic fertilizers, manures, and waste-water treatment facilities can all contribute salt to surface and groundwater. Many industrial processes can increase salinity in process waste-water. In the study area, The lowest concentration of salinity

occurs of the Nambawwam A and B ward area near with 138 ppt. The highest concentration of salinity was found in Dawohgu ward with 574 ppt figure 6 (a) and (b).

Figure. 6 (a) and (b) Salinity conditions of the Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

6. Fe (Iron)

Iron is one of the most abundant metals in Earth's crust, it occurs in water in its ferric and ferrous states, particularly in well-aerated condition. Rock and mineral dissolution acid mine drainage, landfill leachates, sewage and iron related industries are causes of high iron levels in groundwater, lakes and reservoirs, particularly where reducing conditions are present (Okun, 1983). According to chemical results from 125 sample points, there are high Iron in Dawohgu ward area with 0.56mg/l. The lowest value of Iron found in Milone ward area with 0.037 mg/l shown in Figure 7 (a) and (b). The maximum Iron content in drinking water is 0.3 mg/l and is based on color and taste effect rather than on toxicity.

Figure. 7 (a) and (b) Iron (Fe) conditions of Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

7. Lead (Pb)

Lead has major effects on different parts of the body. The bones and teeth of adults contain more than 95% of the total body burden of lead (Castro and Mendez, 2008). The Lead concentration of water sample is in the range between 0.001 mg/l and 0.057 mg/l. Toxicity of lead, also called lead poisoning, can be either acute or chronic. Acute exposure mainly occurs in the place of work and in some manufacturing industries which make use of lead. The highest value of lead causes the toxic effect. The study area, maximum concentration of lead is 0.052 mg/l and minimum as 0.026 mg/l in figure 8 (a) and (b).

Figure. 8 (a) and (b) Lead (Pb) condition of Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

9. Cadmium (Cd)

Cadmium, a toxic trace element, is found in most rocks, as well as in coal and petroleum, in very low concentration, often in combination with zinc. It is released to the environment in wastewater and diffuse pollutions is caused by contamination from fertilizer and local air pollution. According to Taha (2004), natural as well as anthropogenic source of cadmium, including industrial emissions, and the application of fertilizer and sewage to farm land, may lead to contamination of soils, and to increase cadmium up take process of soil cadmium by plants is enhanced at low pH. The highest cadmium value is observed at NyaungyaA ward with 0.44mg/l. The lowest concentration of Cadmium values are 0.10mg/l in with Ladamaward in Figure. 9 (a) and (b). Cadmium accumulates especially in the kidney and is a potent cause of cancer and cardiovascular disease.

Figure. 9 (a) and (b) Cadmium conditions of the Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

10. Magnesium (Mg)

Magnesium also cause the hardness of water and components are widely used in industry and agriculture. Magnesium cannot only be found in seawater, but also in rivers and rain water causing it to naturally spread throughout the environment. WHO (2011) standard level of magnesium is 50 mg/l. Most of the wells in the study area are low in magnesium concentration. The maximum concentration of magnesium value is 20.052 mg/l. Dawohgu ward. The minimum concentration of magnesium value is 1.05 mg/l. in the Minlone ward areashown in figure 10 (a) and (b). Water having more than 150 mg/l. magnesium, is unsafe.

Figure. 10 (a) and (b) Magnesium (Mg) condition of Study Area

Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

Analysis of Water quality Parameter Concentration of the Study Area

Relationship of Well Depth and Geological structure in Study Area

Groundwater is the major source of freshwater that caters to the domestic water demand arising due to escalating population and modern agricultural practices in many developing countries. The geological structures play a major role in the groundwater flow and quality-related problems. The geologic structures like dykes, lineaments, and fractures act as both carriers as well as barriers for groundwater flow. Groundwater is generated through a large number of borewells, tube wells and dug wells, which are spread in the agricultural fields, residential areas, and industrial areas. The heavy withdrawal of groundwater has resulted in lowering of groundwater levels, which in turn has caused deterioration in groundwater quality. In the study area, Maximum depth of the well is found in north part of Center area with 320feet. This area of geology conditions is the Shan Dolomite Group series. Minimum depths are found in east, south and west of the town with 21 feet. It is located with the Mibayataung Group (Southern Shan State). According to the Geological structure, Mibayataung Group (Southern Shan State) area depth of well are more than Shan Dolomite Group

Figure. 11 Depth of the well of Study Area
Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

Figure. 12 Depth of the well of Study Area
Sources : Based on Field Survey, April 2018

Figure. 13 Geology of Study Area

Sources : Based on Myanmar Agricultural Atlas

Suitable area of Drinking water quality in Loikaw Town using the Weighted Overlay Analysis

In this analysis, drinking water quality are most important concern with the pH, Iron, Electric Conductivity, Salinity and Total Dissolved Solids. In weighted Overlay analysis process reveals that percentage influence weights must equal 100%. Therefore it has assigned pH percent and Iron percent are highest weight, Electric Conductivity percent, Total Dissolved Solids percent and salinity percent are same weight. In this analysis, result are (3) suitable area: **Suitable area** found in Minlone, Nantawwam A, Nantpawwan B, Acre 500, Ladauma, Dawdama, Southern part of Dawnoku, Nantkwet, Nyaung b and Minsu ward. **Fairly suitable area** Natnataw, Nyaung A, Htaythama, Dawohgu, east part of Minsu, Damaryon, Mingalar, and Shansu. **Poor area** are found in southern part of Dawohgu.

Figure. 14 Suitable area of Drinking Water of Study Area

Sources : Result of Weighted Overlay Analysis (Geospatial Analysis)

Figure. 15 pH conditions of study area

Sources : Field Survey, April 2018

Figure. 16 EC conditions of study area

Sources : Field Survey, April 2018

Figure. 17 TDS conditions of study area

Sources : Field Survey, April 2018

Figure. 18 Salinity conditions of study area

Sources : Field Survey, April 2018

Figure. 19 Fe conditions of study area

Sources : Field Survey, April 2018

Conclusion

In this analysis, drinking water qualities are most important concern with the pH, Iron, Electric Conductivity, Salinity and Total Dissolved Solids. Compare of the WHO standard of all parameter, most - not significantly over the WHO standard. According the the Weight Overlay Analysis most Suitable area – found in Minlone, Nantawwam A, Nantpawwan B, Acre 500, Ladawma, Dawdama, Southern part of Dawnoku, Nantkwet, Nyaung b and Minsu ward. Fairly suitable area – Natnataw, Nyaung A, Htaythama, Dawohgu, east part of Minsu, Damaryon, Mingalar, and Shansu. Poor area – southern part of Dawohgu ward. In the study area, central part of the town across the BeluChaung east to west. Near the Chaung area live people are used the BeluChaung water as Domestic use, in beluChaung water Quality is suitable for drinking water (Rosy, 2017, M.A Thesis, Loikaw University). According to the Geological structure, Mibayataung Group (Southern Shan State) area depths of wells are more than Shan Dolomite Group. At present, assume the water quality of Loikaw town area of most situations for water quality wasnot too bad conditions. In future, Fluoride, Nitrate and Arsenic parameter should be measure, will be more measure the water quality situations of the study area.

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References

- Hartmut Gaese, Frauke Krass, Mi Mi Kyi (eds.). (2003). *Urban Sustainability in Urban Areas: Basic considerations*. Sustainability in Rural and Urban Environments, First German-Myanmar Workshop in Yangon, Printed in Cologne, Germany, ISBN 3-00-016671-8.
- Khin Snadar Aye et.al.(2015). *A Geographical Analysis on the Transportation Network Development in Kayah State*. Departmental Research Paper, Department of Geography, Loikaw University.
- Khin Khin Htay. (2016). *Geostatistical Analysis of Retail shop Distribution in Loikaw Town*. Research Paper, Department of Geography, Loikaw University.
- M Senthilkumar¹, R Arumugam, D Gnanasundar, D S C Thambi² and E SampathKumar. (2015). *Effects of geological structures on groundwater flow and quality in hardrock regions of northern Tirunelveli district, southern India*. J. Earth Syst. Sci. 124, No. 2, March 2015, pp. 405–418 c Indian Academy of Sciences.
- Myint Myint Oo, Aye Aye Than & Khin Aye Yu. (2009). *The Anaysis of Population Growth in LoikawTownhip*. Research Paper, Department of Geography, Loikaw University.
- Rosy. (2017). *Assessment on Water quality of Belu Stream within the Loikaw City, Kayah State*. M.A thesis , Department of Geography, Loikaw University.
- The[”] Yah. (2012). *An Analysis on Urbanization of Loikaw City*.M.A (Thesis), Department of Geography, Loikaw University.
- World Health Organization. (2011). *Guidelines for Drinking-water Quality. THIRD EDITION INCORPORATING THE FIRST AND SECOND ADDENDA* Volume 1, WHO Library Cataloguing-in-Publication Data, 3rd ed., ISBN 978 92 4 154761 1,

<http://water.usgs.gov/edu/gwhowtofind.html>